

Oxidation of some Organic Compounds by Osmium(VIII) in H_2SO_4 -HOAc Medium. A Kinetic Study

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Manuscript received 26 October 1988, revised 27 March 1989, accepted 21 June 1989

Oxidation of some unsaturated compounds, viz allyl alcohol, acrolein, acrylic acid, maleic acid and cinnamic acid by Os^{VIII} has been studied in H_2SO_4 -HOAc medium. The order in $[Os^{VIII}]$ and [substrate] is unity each in all the cases except acrolein and acrylic acid where the order is fractional. Increasing percentage of acetic acid decreased the rate. The pseudo-first order rate constants decreased slightly with increase in $[H^+]$ at constant ionic strength. Salt effect is negligible and no induced polymerisation noticed when acrylamide added to the reaction system. A direct attack at the C=C by Os^{VIII} in the slow step to give the hydroxylated product has been suggested as a possible route.

OsO_4 is known to be both a hydroxylating agent (in synthetic organic chemistry) and efficient catalyst in the oxidation of several organic compounds by various oxidants in aqueous alkaline as well as acid media¹⁻⁴. In the Os^{VIII} catalysed reactions in acid medium, it has been suggested that OsO_4 oxidises the substrate directly in a slow step as in case of alkaline medium. Recently we have reported⁵ the oxidation of some hydroxy compounds by OsO_4 in aqueous alkaline medium and concluded that OsO_4 can oxidise the substrate even in the absence of any oxidant. In order to see this, a study of oxidation of some organic functional groups by OsO_4 was taken up in acid medium. Incidentally, OsO_4 could not oxidise n-propanol and other simple monohydric alcohols. However, allyl alcohol which has a double bond is oxidised smoothly. If one attributes this to the preferential attack at the double bond by Os^{VIII} then there should be no reaction at all with substrates having no double bonds irrespective of the other functional group present. Hence, in the present work reaction of OsO_4 with propan-1-ol, allyl alcohol, propionaldehyde, acrolein, propionic acid, acrylic acid, phenylpropionic acid, cinnamic acid, succinic acid and maleic acid have been studied in order to get a better insight into the mechanism of oxidation and to find out the selectivity of OsO_4 in acid medium.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade, and wherever necessary purified further employing standard methods. All aqueous solutions were prepared in triple-distilled water. Stock solutions of water-insoluble compounds were prepared in acetic acid. Acetic acid was refluxed for several hours with CrO_3 before distillation. Stock solution

of Os^{VIII} was prepared by dissolving osmic acid (Johnson Mathey) in H_2SO_4 (6.60×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3}) and standardised iodometrically⁷.

The reactions were carried out under the conditions $[Os^{VIII}] \ll [substrate]$ at the desired temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). In a typical kinetic run, the unreacted Os^{VIII} was estimated by first quenching the reaction mixture (5 cm³ aliquots) in 10 ml of 10% KI + 1 ml 2N HCl and estimating the liberated iodine by titrating it against the standard sodium thiosulphate solution. The kinetic runs were followed in duplicate and the rate constants are reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$.

Products and stoichiometry: The oxidation product, i.e. the corresponding dihydroxy compound was identified by the characteristic spot-test⁸ as well as from the spectral data. In case of allyl alcohol, the product was estimated as follows. A mixture of allyl alcohol (4.43×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}), OsO_4 (2.00×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}), H_2SO_4 (0.50 mol dm^{-3}) and acetic acid (50%, v/v) was kept at 299.5 K for over 24 h with intermittent shaking. The mixture was then neutralised with $NaHCO_3$ solution with ice-cooling such that the temperature did not exceed 27° . The precipitated salts were removed by filtration and the filtrate extracted with ether. The etherial layer was dried ($MgSO_4$), the solvent distilled off and the residue (1 ml) taken into a hard glass tube and mixed with finely powdered potassium bisulphate. A piece of filter paper moistened with the reagent (freshly prepared mixture of 1 drop of 5% sodium nitroprusside and 1 drop of 20% piperidine) was placed over the open end of the tube and covered with a glass cap. The acrolein, produced on heating, coloured the paper deep gelatin blue. On treating with 2N sodium hydroxide the blue area changed to peach-blossom colour.

The test confirmed the oxidation product of allyl alcohol as glycerol. Stoichiometric studies revealed that one mole of Os^{VIII} was consumed for every mole of unsaturated compound.

Results and Discussion

Under the conditions $[Os^{VIII}] \ll [substrate]$, the plot of $\log(a-x)$ vs time is linear indicating

first order in $[Os^{VIII}]$ (Fig. 1A). Such plots were obtained for all the reactions studied. From the slopes of these plots the pseudo-first order rate constants (k') were evaluated. The plot of $\log k'$ vs $\log [substrate]$ is also linear with a slope of 1.0 in case of allyl alcohol (Fig. 1B), maleic acid and cinnamic acid (Table 1) and fractional in the case of acrolein and acrylic acid. The pseudo-first order rate constants decreased slightly with the increase in $[H^+]$ at constant ionic strength (Table 2). This slight decrease in the rate could be due to the

Fig. 1. (A) Plot of $\log(a-x)$ vs time; $[Os^{VIII}] = 3.94 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H_2SO_4] = 0.50 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[HOAc] = 50\%$, temp. = 299.5 K, $[acrolein] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. (B) Plot of $4 + \log k'$ vs $3 + \log [allyl alcohol]$; $10^2/[acrolein]$; $[Os^{VIII}] = 3.94 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H_2SO_4] = 0.50 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 299.5 K. (C) Plot of $10^{-2}/k'$ vs $10^{-2}/[cinnamic acid]$; $[Os^{VIII}] = 3.94 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H_2SO_4] = 0.50 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[HOAc] = 60\%$, temp. = 299.5 K. (D) Plot of $10^{-2}/k'$ vs $10^{-2}/[cinnamic acid]$; $[Os^{VIII}] = 3.94 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H_2SO_4] = 0.50$

TABLE 1 - EFFECT OF [SUBSTRATE] ON THE RATE CONSTANTS

[Os^{VIII}] = 3.94×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, [HOAc] = 50%,
[H₂SO₄] = 0.50 mol dm⁻³; temp. = 299.5 K

	[substrate] $\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	k' $\times 10^4$ s ⁻¹	k' $\times 10^4$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Acrolein	1.00	5.91	—
	2.00	9.03	—
	4.00	16.00	—
	10.0	24.00	—
Acrylic acid	0.20	7.00	—
	0.50	14.40	—
	1.00	24.00	—
	2.00	38.40	—
Maleic acid	5.00	4.80	0.95
	10.00	11.30	1.13
	15.00	16.00	1.06
	30.00	27.40	0.91
Cinnamic acid	1.00	3.46	3.46
	2.00	7.93	3.91
	4.00	12.00	3.00
	10.00	29.50	3.00

TABLE 2 - EFFECT OF [H⁺] ON RATE CONSTANT IN OXIDATION OF ALLYL ALCOHOL BY Os^{VIII} IN H₂SO₄ MEDIUM

[Os^{VIII}] = 3.94×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, [allyl alcohol] = 1.47×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³; temp. = 299.5 K

[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.25	0.50	1.00	1.70	2.50
k' ($\times 10^4$ s ⁻¹)	8.15	8.08	7.94	7.90	7.86

possible removal of reactive OsO₄ species via protonation. Added salts, like NaClO₄, Na₂SO₄, NaHSO₄ had negligible effect on the rate indicating the reaction to be either ion-dipole or dipole-dipole type. No reaction was observed between Os^{VIII} and the corresponding saturated organic compounds.

Increase in percentage of acetic acid from 20 to 60% decreased the rate (Table 3) and the plot of log k' vs $(D-1)/(2D+1)$ was linear passing through the

TABLE 3 - EFFECT OF ACETIC ACID ON RATE CONSTANT IN OXIDATION OF ALLYL ALCOHOL BY Os^{VIII} IN H₂SO₄ MEDIUM

[Os^{VIII}] = 3.94×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 0.50 mol dm⁻³;
[allyl alcohol] = 1.47×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, temp. = 299.5 K

Acetic acid % (v/v)	Dielectric constant D	$(D-1)/(2D+1)$	k' $\times 10^4$ s ⁻¹
0	—	—	8.08
20	62.7	0.488	7.67
40	48.0	0.484	5.18
50	41.5	0.482	4.26
60	34.4	0.478	3.49

origin indicating that the reaction is between two neutral molecules. This coupled with the absence of salt-effect suggest the reaction to be of dipole-dipole type. The absorption spectrum of OsO₄ at different concentrations of acid is almost identical suggesting that neutral OsO₄ is the reactive species involved. This also supports the dipole-dipole nature of the reaction assumed. Since unsaturated organic compounds are known to be resistant to oxidation by one-electron oxidants⁹, a free radical pathway in the present study is discounted. This is supported by the absence of polymerisation when acrylonitrile or acrylamide was added to the reaction mixture. However, addition of acrylamide (AA) slightly increased the rate probably due to a reaction between Os^{VIII} and acrylamide which also has a C=C (under the conditions [allyl alcohol] = 1.47×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 0.50 mol dm⁻³, [HOAc] = 60%, temp. = 303 K; the rate constant for the oxidation of allyl alcohol alone is $k' = 2.40 \times 10^{-4}$ s⁻¹ while in the presence of [AA] = 1.00×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, $k' = 2.74 \times 10^{-4}$ s⁻¹). Since the product of oxidation is the corresponding dihydroxy compound, the following mechanism is suggested.

Scheme 1

From the above mechanism the rate equation comes out to be

$$\frac{-2.303 \, d \log [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]}{dt} = k' \frac{kK [\text{substrate}]}{1 + K [\text{substrate}]} \quad (1)$$

In case of acrolein/acrylic acid—Os^{VIII} reaction the order in [substrate] is fractional and the plot of $1/k'$ vs $1/[\text{substrate}]$ is linear with a positive intercept (Fig. 1C) on $1/k'$ axis according to equation (2) which is a reciprocal of equation (1), thus giving support for the formation of a complex between Os^{VIII} and the substrate prior to oxidation.

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{kK [\text{substrate}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (2)$$

From the slope and intercept values of the above plot the value of k and K were calculated (In the case of acrolein—Os^{VIII} reaction at 299.5 K. the values of k and K were found to be 3.30×10^{-4} s⁻¹ and 0.428 dm³ mol⁻¹ respectively). In case of allyl alcohol, maleic acid and cinnamic acid, a clean first order in [substrate] and linear plot of $1/k'$ vs

TABLE 4 - REACTION RATES AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF UNSATURATED ORGANIC COMPOUNDS BY Os^{VIII} IN H₂SO₄ - HOAc MEDIUM[H₂SO₄] = 0.50 mol dm⁻³, [HOAc] = 50%, temp. = 299.5 K

Substrate	k' $\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	E_{exp} kJ mol^{-1}	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol^{-1}	ΔS^\ddagger $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$
Allyl alcohol	67.7	43.8	41.0	82.1	-137
Acrylic acid	19.2	59.8	57.3	85.2	-93.1
Acrolein	3.99	54.7	52.2	86.7	-115
Cinnamic acid	.92	21.4	26.9	89.8	-210
Maleic acid	1.13	80.5	78.0	92.3	-47.7

1/[substrate] passing through the origin (Fig. 1D) have been observed.

In alkaline medium, OsO₄ is known to oxidise almost all hydroxy compounds irrespective of the presence or absence of a double bond. In order to find out whether this is so in acid medium, oxidation of a number of compounds containing C=C and a functional group have been studied and the rates compared with their saturated analogues. No reaction was observed with the saturated compounds. However, OsO₄ oxidises the corresponding unsaturated compounds giving a dihydroxy compound suggesting preferential attack of C=C by Os^{VIII} in acid medium even when other functional groups are present.

Table 4 reveals that the reactivity of different unsaturated compounds is in the order, allyl alcohol > acrylic acid > acrolein > cinnamic acid > maleic acid. The order of reactivity can be explained by taking the steric factors into consideration. When bulky groups are attached to C=C there could be some steric hindrance for the Os^{VIII} to approach the double bond in forming the precursor complex. The low rate of oxidation of cinnamic acid compared to acrylic acid could be due to the presence of phenyl ring which acts as an electron-sink thus reducing the electron density at C=C resulting in the reduction chances of formation of precursor complex. In case of maleic acid due to presence of two carboxyl groups on the same side, the *cis* attack by OsO₄ is prevented thus decreasing the rate of oxidation. This supports the contention

of *cis* attack by OsO₄ during the hydroxylation of unsaturated organic compounds. The activation parameters calculated for all the substrates are recorded in Table 4. ΔG^\ddagger values are more or less same for all the substrates indicating a similar mechanism is operative in all the cases. Large negative ΔS^\ddagger values support the contention that the activated complexes are actually addition complexes of the substrate and OsO₄.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P.V.S.) is thankful to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a research fellowship.

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